

Case Study 5: Data curation and availability at instrument-based facilities

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1 Introduction

1.1 Aim

To understand facility data management necessary to publish standalone datasets, to support *e.g.* formal publishing routes or for machine learning within the National Research Facility for lab-based X-ray CT

1.2 Description of case study

The Southampton node of the NXCT, the μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre, has an O(PB) extant archive of computed tomography data. Explore if what has been captured is good enough to publish datasets. Build prototype tooling to “bridge the gap”, then see if it is translatable to other instrument-based facilities.

1.3 Outline plan of work

1. Tracking data entities with local unique identifiers (individual CT scan, CT job “context” &c.) - assign or add if not present
2. Assess what already exists – is it fit for DOI? If not, identify what needs to be done
3. Create a queryable interface to this to gather metadata, agglomeration (human friendly HTML, machine friendly JSON) – simple demonstrator, prototype to interface with whatever exists
4. Clear route to metadata and data retrieval – what needs to be implemented? How to handle *e.g.* logistics for large datasets, offline/archived dataset management, embargoes?
5. Reveal routes to abstractions – identify metadata that is either derivable (domain understanding) or extractable (instrument/data format understanding) for applicability to NCS and beyond – is it practical to make a generalisable “shim” layer without compromising metadata richness

1.4 Background and history

Previously (often prohibitively) expensive supercomputing was brought into the mainstream after the development of the BEOWULF parallel cluster [1], allowing more institutions to create their own customised compute platforms to solve scientific problems. Further efforts were expended in the late 1990s and early 2000s with the concurrent rise of e-Science and Grid computing [2], the former formalising many computational problem spaces and the latter bringing together disparate resources. Particular Grid solutions were developed to solve specific problems, for example GridPP [3] for particle physics, or GEODISE [4] for design optimisation engineering. alongside more general-purpose Grids (*e.g.* the National e-Infrastructure service or the European Grid Infrastructure).

Data-intensive science in some spheres is a well-managed problem, where there has been appropriate acknowledgement and planning at the inception of the project. The best-known

example of this is arguably CERN's Large Hadron Collider project, where the “data deluge” identified by Jim Grey [5] was not only anticipated but optimised at all levels, from data acquisition at the sensor level down, where 99% of data are filtered away, to disparate, international post-processing and analysis of (in 2018) 88 petabytes of data – encapsulated by the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid project [6].

Laboratories and instrument-based facilities have their own data deluges. Though the scale may be smaller than the LHC, the data throughput in some instances is potentially closer than may be initially realised – the μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre at the University of Southampton can generate terabytes of data per instrument per day (or a potential petabyte per year per instrument). Even with facilities producing fewer data, there remains an issue of processing, storing, managing, curating and exposing these data. The FAIR data principles can help guide all facilities, and, if implemented, provide a route to exposing these data as a service to existing and future cluster, Grid, cloud and e-Science compute resources, as well as to individual researchers' workstations.

1.5 FAIR data

The 2016 FAIR principles [7, 8] – **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable – provide guidance for data and metadata, and we summarise them here to aid assessment.

F1	(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
F2	Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol
A1.1	The protocol is open, free and universally implementable
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary
A2	Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence
R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

The stated goal of the FAIR guidelines is to improve these qualities for digital assets, with particular emphasis on the ability of machines to act upon them.

2 Workflow

Instrument-based facilities follow a generalisable workflow: a user has a sample, which needs to be examined by an instrument, operated by an instrument expert. This instrument will generate domain data, which is analysed by a domain data expert, and the sample and resulting data may be returned to the user or third party (or optionally destroyed).

In some instances, the user with the sample in our generalised example could be the instrument expert, or the domain data expert, or both.

2.1 μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre

The user who has a sample they wish to have CT scanned initially makes contact with the imaging centre, perhaps via email, telephone call or in-person visit. After an initial consultation where the feasibility of the CT scan is assessed, and an appropriate instrument is determined, either the user or the beamline scientist (instrument expert) completes a CT scan application form.

This application form generates an entry in the imaging centre's job tracking system. Further communication between the beamline scientist and the user establishes the sample delivery to the facility in order to be scanned, and the beamtime itself is scheduled. At the scheduled time, the sample is scanned – a process which captures radiographs and the acquisition geometry, and this allows reconstruction of the radiographic projection data.

Once the imaging has been completed, the sample is then free to be returned to or collected by the user, along with the reconstructed data ready for further analysis.

In the case of internal academic or research data (non-commercial), the metadata of the scans along with the data are extracted and stored in perpetuity.

3 Tracking data entities with LUIDs

A *data entity* in this context is anything that needs or may need to be exposed by the dataset, consisting of metadata, plus optional data – in the CT scanning context, this could be an individual CT scan (consisting of a number of acquired radiographic projections, a CT reconstruction and the CT scanning parameters used, for example X-ray energy, distances between X-ray source and object, detector geometry), a group of CT scans making up a larger group (for example, a number of CT scans along the height of a tall object, or a number of time steps in an *in situ* experiment), or a CT scanning job (which would consist of user-supplied metadata from an initial enquiry, *e.g.* name, email address, desired resolution, technical requirements, health and safety considerations).

LUIDs (locally unique identifiers) can be as straightforward as incrementing numbers. Whatever entity needs to be tracked needs to have one of these assigned per distinct entry, so the exact data entity can be retrieved and the retriever is assured it is the correct one.

Databases handle this automatically with incrementing primary keys, the typical “id” column in a database table – one table per entity type is enough to meet this sufficiency.

If these are not present in the target system, they must be assigned retrospectively, and automatically assigned going forwards for subsequent data entity entries.

In our CT facility exemplar, an individual CT scan must be associated with a CT scanning job, so that one may be found from the other by authorised individuals. The CT scans on their own should be somewhat pseudonymised or pseudonymisable; the former by virtue of no distinct identifying information being present in the CT scan metadata, the latter by omitting any non-automated fields that *could* contain personally identifiable data (e.g. a filename). The numeric-only ID makes it trivial to achieve this condition.

By ensuring local data entities have unique identifiers, building globally unique identifiers is straightforward, and if the local data entity identifiers are made persistent, *i.e.* so it is forbidden to change these identifiers, then it meets entirely condition **F1** in the FAIR standard. A digital object identifier (DOI) could be assigned as an adjunct.

Note that only one reconstructed CT dataset is explicitly included (if present) with the CT scan metadata; in principle multiple reconstructions of a single dataset could exist but this is not managed directly – it is considered derived, in much the same way a user quantification or surface mesh generation may be and is therefore beyond the scope of this project.

4 Assessment of existing system: μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre

The μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre hosts four relevant data entities, listed in table 1.

Table 1: Subset of μ -VIS data entities

Data entity	Description	Content providers	LUID present?	LUID name ¹
Jobs	Applications for CT scans	Requesting user; domain expert	Yes	job_id
CT scan group	One or more CT scans	Requesting user; domain expert; machine	Yes	data_id
CT scans	CT scan metadata	Machine (generated by CT system, parsed/indexed by database host)	Yes	scan_id
Archive disks	Offline archive of CT scan groups	Machine; domain expert	Yes	disk_id

1 Unofficial, as within their respective data entities they are referred to as “id”

4.1 Jobs

All user enquiries generate a unique entry in a job table. This entry can be associated then with subsequent CT scans and is compulsory: no CT scanning work will commence without this identifier being available. The metadata in this entity consists of user-supplied information about what they want to do, which may (amongst many other things) describe the specimen, what they wish to find with it, publication expectations, funding bodies, material composition and desired resolution.

The quality of this metadata is variable and initially unverifiable; some users, familiar with CT and with good *a priori* knowledge of their specimen, will provide high-quality metadata. Conversely, novice users or those with unknown specimens, the metadata are sparser, and “less correct”.

A job can have other data appended by the beamline scientist, which *may* include updated information about the specimen, but is not obligatory.

One job may contain many CT scans.

4.2 CT scan group

This data table stores information about a particular location for online (“live”) data – the username, creation date, archive status and size. All CT scans have an associated CT scan group. These are dynamically generated from their position on the online file store – the parent directory containing CT scans (and other data, scripts, and so on). One CT scan group may contain many CT scans.

4.3 CT scans

This entity is stored in a SQL database, with a large number of columns, mapping to useful metadata – that which beamline scientists may use to recreate the scan conditions, or those working on reconstructing datasets can gather the system geometry. These are associated with `job_id` and `data_id`.

Many CT scans may be in a single job or single CT scan group.

4.4 Archive disks

Archive disks are associated with `data_id` and store complete datasets in an offline archive. The μ -VIS system has provided this as a convenience though the responsibility for data lie with the researcher using the facility, not with the laboratory itself or their beamline scientists. This archive is provided on a “best effort” basis. As such, data *may* be available to be retrieved from here (in reality, thus far all data attempted to be retrieved has been successful, but this is by luck; the primary retrieval route for offline data should be via the original researchers or their institution, information captured via `job_id`).

One archive disk may contain many CT scan groups.

Figure 1: Partial entity relationship diagram for μ -VIS data/metadata

4.5 (Meta)data scales

μ -VIS currently stores nearly 30,000 metadata entries in a database, each representing a CT scan ($O(10^3)$ /year), with some annotated image data permanently stored on disk for these. The majority of these range between approximately 20 and 200 megabytes – a few are larger from exceptional datasets. In every case, the size of the online metadata are less than 1% of the original dataset size.

Online data across all performance tiers is around 500TB, with in excess of a petabyte stored offline on disk or tape. Offline data are currently retrieved on request and released to authorised parties on a best-effort basis.

4.6 Summary

Between these four database tables, and the associations they have with the underlying data, there is evidence that the data are described with rich metadata (**F2**, **R1.2**, **R1**) though notably, there is no formal data usage license (**R1.1**) – this is something that can be rectified. **R1.3** is met because the data are broad, but there are no community standards for this domain that are this broadly applicable. DICOM and DICONDE formats provide some guidance for medical and non-destructive evaluation respectively, and these are derivable from a subset of the captured data. For this pilot, the data entity “CT scans” will be exposed.

At present, although there is no broader accessibility protocol in place, **A1** and **A1.1** are met – the (meta)data are retrievable using standardised communications protocols (HTTP). The metadata are held behind beamline scientist authentication and authorisation (**A1.2**). The μ -VIS data life cycle means that once the data moves from online to offline, all of the metadata captured at the time remains available permanently (**A2**).

Where the existing system is insufficient is with interoperability. Although **I3** is met internally with links between data entities, **I1** and **I2** are not yet defined – there is not yet a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation (**I1**), and as this vocabulary does not exist, it cannot follow FAIR principles in turn (**I2**). It is apparent then that the scope of the pilot needs to add this layer on top.

5 Bridging the gap

For the micro-CT domain, a comprehensive and formalised standard is still lacking. Arguably, the DICONDE standard, based on an overloading of DICOM, meets some of these requirements, it is primarily suited to non-destructive evaluation and so lacks sufficiency in the more generalised domain. Additionally, it by necessity has to skip many of the rich metadata fields CT scanner manufacturers encapsulate in their formats.

The μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre has scans from multiple manufacturers, and as such identifying common fields which can be exposed, or derived and then exposed, is more straightforward. These common fields are ones that a beamline scientist would need to recreate an experiment on another instrument (as opposed to the complete fieldset, which would allow them to copy the experiment exactly on the same instrument); if they understand the differences between the instruments (for example, scan geometry, transmission vs. reflection sources) the former should be enough to reasonably repeat a measurement within acceptable tolerances.

The demonstrator extracts a handful of key areas and expose these as an *ersatz* vocabulary for CT. A more fully featured approach could cover as many nascent standardisation efforts as possible, and supply additional metadata as optional per machine manufacturer.

With an inevitably varied tapestry of metadata recording amongst instrument-based facilities, two coarse levels are proposed: the first, a translation or “shim” layer to take whatever format the data currently exists in, and present it to a form suitable for transmission (e.g. dictionary) along with a descriptor dictionary; the second, an external communications layer, to allow access over a network or service.

The communication layer should be able to handle a query from an external user, and pass this to the translation layer. The translation layer can then interrogate the (meta)data store, and return the query results through the communications layer in the agreed format.

Figure 2: Demonstrator schematic. The two layers in the middle provide I1 and I2 FAIR compliance to the existing database

In the demonstrator, two response options are presented – the first, an HTML response, for browsing datasets and queries; the second, a JSON response suitable for services and other tools to work with.

5.1 Translation layer mechanism

The μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre stores its metadata in a MySQL database (MariaDB) – rather than exposing this directly, the translation layer serves to provide a unit-normalised view, applying descriptions and curated notes. In the demonstrator, a separate user and a terse, subset SELECT statement yields the metadata. In a fully-formatted system, this would be better replaced by a database view, though the mechanism provides the flexibility to adapt this to any underlying datastore, from flat files, through databases, to more complex aggregated datastores.

This is implemented in Python, and returns two dictionaries. One, the description dictionary, mapping directly to each returned column, providing a richer description of the field, and the unit it is expressed in. The second, the data dictionary, containing the results of the query.

The query interface currently addresses only one field of search parameter but could trivially be extended to more fields.

5.2 Communications layer mechanism

This is a simple Flask application, presenting a web page if browsed to, and having a number of query mechanisms and return types. It takes in the translation layer Python and provides a simple service. A free text query is parsed from an HTTP GET request and passed through to the translation layer.

The resultant data is rendered to HTML or returned as a JSON [9] dictionary depending on the request. A handful of exemplar queries are offered by way of a “getting started” assistance.

- Show CT scans matching "_1234_" [[HTML](#) | [JSON](#)]
search string is _1234_
- Scans from 20th August 2015 [[HTML](#) | [JSON](#)]
search string is 20150820_
- Coffee bean scans [[HTML](#) | [JSON](#)]
search string is coffeebean
- Datasets that have been generated for user training [[HTML](#) | [JSON](#)]
search string is training

Figure 3: Sample queries

Selecting one of these is analogous to entering the search string in the appropriate field. It will bring up either an HTML or JSON view accordingly. The HTML view shows the representative images as well as the returned fields.

straylight:5000/query/text?query=coffeebean

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home | readme | browse | text search | source

Text query

13 results found

zero_proj	ninety_proj	centreslice	id	filename	data_id	bu
			15746	20171114_VERSA_1692_20171114_VERSA_1692_coffeebean.bxm	11346	165
			15747	20171114_VERSA_1692_20171114_VERSA_1692_coffeebean.bxm	11346	165

Figure 4: HTML view of results of "coffeebean" search string

The simple text query interface allows you to specify whether you want JSON (defaulting to HTML), and adjust the JSON style (defaulting to records)

Text query

0 results found

Tabloo?
 JSON?

records

Figure 5: Simple text query interface

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home | readme | browse | text search | source

Text query

8 results found

zero_proj	ninety_proj	centreslice	id	filename	data_id	bugzilla_id	date_added	VoxelsX	VoxelsY	VoxelsZ	Units	VoxelSi
			14159	20130430_HMX_446_RB_4fpp_40Kvp_Mo_Bumblebee_01.txt	10424	446	2018-01-09 23:16:52	1621	1597	1983	mm	0.018

Figure 6: Result of query from figure 5

Enabling the "JSON" option in the query will directly return this (in this instance, a web browser rendering of the JSON)

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `straylight:5000/query/text?query=Bumblebee&asjson=on&orient=records`. The browser's developer tools are open to the 'JSON' tab, displaying a JSON object with the following fields and values:

```

{
  "AngularStep": 0.11457670273711,
  "DetectorPixelSizeX": 0.2,
  "DetectorPixelSizeY": 0.2,
  "DetectorPixelsX": 2000,
  "DetectorPixelsY": 2000,
  "FramesPerProjection": 4,
  "InitialAngle": 4.98897504806519,
  "Projections": 3142,
  "SrcToDetector": 672.56,
  "SrcToObject": 39.8482437133789,
  "Units": "mm",
  "VoxelSizeX": 0.0118,
  "VoxelSizeY": 0.0118,
  "VoxelSizeZ": 0.0118,
  "VoxelsX": 1621,
  "VoxelsY": 1597,
  "VoxelsZ": 1983,
  "Xraykv": 40,
  "XrayuA": 173,
  "accumulation": 0,
  "binning": 0,
  "bugzilla_id": 446,
  "bugzilla_url": "https://muvis.soton.ac.uk/bugzilla/show_bug.cgi?id=446",
  "centreslice": "https://muvis.soton.ac.uk/muvis/metadata/14159/centreslice.png",
  "data_id": 10424,
  "data_url": "https://muvis.soton.ac.uk/bugzilla/muvis_data.cgi?id=10424",
  "date_added": "Tue, 09 Jan 2018 23:16:52 GMT"
}

```

Figure 7: Result of query with JSON enabled

5.3 Comments

The translation layer and communication layer together provide a commonly-addressable, lightweight middleware mechanism for access, search and retrieval for existing data and metadata installations.

6 Key recommendations

- Ensure data and metadata are being captured and stored by the facility, and identify the gaps between this and FAIR data
- Create lightweight “shim” layers to provide a common interface – HTML and JSON – to the data – this will satisfy human and machine requirements
- Leverage domain-appropriate standards where available, and in all cases expose potentially useful metadata

6.1 Data/metadata capture

The Southampton NXCT have been capturing all data and metadata for over ten years. Metadata are from two sources: the first is user-supplied, where they have described the sample they wish to scan and outline their expectations. These metadata are potentially subject to embargo or other restriction, and carry the risk of being “wrong”.

Ensuring that this is captured even if it is not currently well-understood is important: some metadata are instrument-specific and their meaning, whilst not necessarily initially clear, can later become clear as, for example, an instrument manufacturer offers an explanation for a field, or context or experience means the operators can provide additional insight.

Recommendation: Ensure data and metadata are being captured and stored by the facility, and identify the gaps between this and FAIR data.

Benefits: Capturing data and metadata immediately ensures these are not lost, and new understanding can be applied retrospectively. Identifying the gaps between what is currently captured (and not captured), and FAIR data provides a pathway to full FAIR compliance for any instrument-based facility.

Infrastructure: facility dependent. Training users in FAIR principles, and ensuring there is the means – software (databases and hardware – to enable the capture of data and metadata. Without these, there is nothing to share.

6.2 Create lightweight “shim” layers to provide a common interface

Established instrument-based facilities may already have – and hopefully already have – in turn an established data and metadata management framework, in partial compliance with FAIR. Recognising that it might be difficult or impractical to change this (especially as some metadata may be in a fixed proprietary format supplied by the instrument manufacturer), create instead a very thin “shim” that will exist between what exists already and what is desired.

During the development of this shim layer, domain requirements may be established iteratively; it may be the case that when thinking about this and talking to potential consumers of the service, new requirements of the metadata may emerge, and encourage the facility to adapt.

Recommendation: Create lightweight “shim” layers to provide a common interface – HTML and JSON – to the data. This will satisfy both human and machine accessibility requirements.

Benefits: Light touch layers that work with existing frameworks are more likely to be implemented, and where they are implemented, the development time frame is shorter. Simple methods which give powerful, usable output will encourage reuse and accelerate times to discovery

Infrastructure: possible software support to develop these shims, particularly if an established system has no active maintainers (e.g. a postdoc moving on). Hardware may be necessary if returned data is large (scaling and bandwidth issues should be considered)

6.3 Leverage domain-appropriate standards, and expose all metadata

In many areas, there are existing standards that can be implemented, or where insufficient, used as a basis to provide compatibility and guidance. A wider consultation on a per-domain or per-facility basis would be advisable to assess these standards.

Many instruments generate metadata that does not follow a standard, but it should be kept, and presented in a useful manner (e.g. translated to an SI unit with a rich description), possibly as a superset of any existing standard to ensure that all possible metadata are available for reuse.

Recommendation: Leverage domain-appropriate standards where available, and in all cases expose potentially useful metadata

Benefits: if the standards already exist, then familiarity follows. If they do not, there is an opportunity to develop an initial offering and allow it to be guided by the community. Exposing all metadata as a superset of a standard maximises flexibility and knowledge

Infrastructure: consultations and community engagement to establish the extent and availability of existing standards, and to provide guidance where those standards do not exist

7 Additional areas for future consideration

There are a number of areas which would clearly need to be addressed in a final implementation of the system, but which are considered beyond the scope of this demonstrator.

7.1 Metadata confidence

There are various levels of metadata which could be available to the data consumer, but which are not readily separable at this stage. Notably, a coarse notion of “woolly” metadata versus “curated” metadata; the former being *e.g.* user-supplied but *maybe* incorrect (for example, a user supplies a description of the sample that is incorrect, perhaps suggesting it is made out of only aluminium, when it contains a titanium insert, or providing an incorrect size measurement unit), and the latter being verified by a domain expert.

Conflict resolution *e.g.* what to do if a user supplies metadata with a job, scan or data gathering request claiming to be one material, but the result of the CT scan indicate it is something else? Correcting the user-supplied data is undesirable. A supplementary note is better. However, differentiating these in a machine search is something that should be considered: if a data consumer coarsely searches for datasets containing “neodymium”, how can they separate matches for samples which do contain neodymium, from those that were incorrectly asserted by the facility user?

7.2 Embargoing

Clearly there will be some datasets that are unsuitable for immediate release, perhaps for intellectual property or security reasons, or other external requirements. A mechanism to prevent some datasets from being exposed to the wider world by the internal system is essential – some may be prevented from exposure permanently, some until another set of requirements are met, more still by an “embargo until” date.

7.3 Security

No authorisation or authentication is present in the demonstrator. Formal datasets are not exposed or linked, only metadata in this system. It is isolated to an internal network for demonstration purposes. In a finalised system, there may be constraints on accessing the (meta)data – anonymous access may be desirable in some cases, in others, an authentication of username or accessing facility, or separate authorisation for restricted datasets may be necessary.

7.4 Scaling

No direct consideration has been made of the scalability of this system, or of the underlying system. These should be assessed and handled according to expected access requirements. It should be noted that in the case of broad searches, underlying data requests could easily measure in the hundreds of terabytes, or in the case of the most aggressive wildcards, petabytes. Clearly this would be as impractical as commonplace without safeguarding, warning or other limitations.

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9 Appendix

9.1 PSDI demonstrator, client example

A few quick examples to demonstrate connectivity to the remote source.

We'll use pandas (<https://pandas.pydata.org/>) to get something interesting out of the JSON for this. We'll open the data directly from the demonstrator URL.

In [2]:

```
import pandas as pd
import json
from urllib.request import urlopen
```

Next, we'll set up a simple query, and hook it into the remote URL. Once we've done that, we can load the result in as JSON and segue it into two pandas DataFrames - one for the data, another for the descriptions.

In [16]:

```
query = "_HUTCH_"
remote_data_url =
"http://straylight:5000/query/text?query="+query+"&asjson=on&orient=records"
response = urlopen(remote_data_url)
json_result = json.loads(response.read())
df = pd.DataFrame(json_result['data'])
descs = pd.DataFrame(json_result['descriptions'])
```

Let's take a quick look at what we've got back from the server now it is in our DataFrame.

In [68]:

```
print(df.columns)
df.head()
```

```
Index(['AngularStep', 'DetectorPixelSizeX', 'DetectorPixelSizeY',
      'DetectorPixelsX', 'DetectorPixelsY', 'FramesPerProjection',
      'InitialAngle', 'Projections', 'SrcToDetector', 'SrcToObject', 'Units',
      'VoxelSizeX', 'VoxelSizeY', 'VoxelSizeZ', 'VoxelsX', 'VoxelsY',
      'VoxelsZ', 'XraykV', 'XrayuA', 'accumulation', 'binning', 'bugzilla_id',
      'bugzilla_url', 'centreslice', 'data_id', 'data_url', 'date_added',
      'digitalGain', 'exposure', 'filename', 'gain', 'id', 'lines',
      'metadata_url', 'ninety_proj', 'zero_proj'],
      dtype='object')
```

Out[68]:

(table removed for brevity) 5 rows × 36 columns

Now, we'll define something from the results. We could of course browse these further, or do whatever string matching we want to do to determine the field name, but for now we will use one we know - exposure. We'll define this in a string and then reference it on both the data and descriptions side.

As a quick example, let's make a histogram of the exposure, and take the unit from the data too.

In [49]:

```
interesting_thing = "exposure"  
ax=df[interesting_thing].plot.hist(bins=40, logy=True, edgecolor='black')  
label = ax.set_xlabel("%s (%s)" % (interesting_thing, descs[interesting_thing].unit))
```


With CT data, the number of acquired image frames making up a projection can vary. By multiplying that with the exposure, we can work out how long it takes to capture each projection.

In [35]:

```
ax = (df.FramesPerProjection * (df.exposure/1000)).plot.hist(bins=20, logy=True, alpha=0.75,  
edgecolor='black', color=(0.9,1,0.2))  
label = ax.set_xlabel('time per projection (seconds)')
```


The total scan time (excluding some time for adjusting the rotation stage and detector between projections) is then the time for each projection, multiplied by the total number of projections:

In [70]:

```
ax = (df.FramesPerProjection * (df.exposure/(3600*1000)) * df.Projections).plot.hist(bins=20,  
                                            logy=True,  
                                            alpha=0.75,  
                                            edgecolor='black',  
                                            color=(0.5,1,0.2))  
label = ax.set_xlabel('time per scan (low estimate, hours)')
```


We can pull out a scatter plot of the X-ray energy and the flux. Increased X-ray energy increases the penetration through the material being imaged, and increased flux (photon count per unit time) results in better signal-to-noise ratios for a time. However, lowering either of these allows the X-ray focal spot to reduce in size, improving spot resolution.

In [46]:

```
ax = df.plot.scatter(x='XraykV', y='XrayuA', edgecolor='black', color=(1,.5,.75))  
xlabel = ax.set_xlabel(descs.XraykV.unit)  
ylabel = ax.set_ylabel(descs.XrayuA.unit)
```


The X-ray sources have power limits. We can trivially get the powers the sources have been operated at by multiplying flux and energy.

In [74]:

```
ax = (df.XraykV*df.XrayuA/1000).plot.hist(logy=True, alpha=0.5, edgecolor='black', color='#60f')
ax.set_xlabel('power (watts)')
```

Out[74]:

Text(0.5, 0, 'Power (watts)')

Another critical part of the setup of a CT scan is the trade off of distances between source, object and detector. A larger source to imaging (detector) distance is useful for large physical objects, or to get a high resolution through magnification, but the inverse square law means that flux falls away rapidly as this distance increases.

In [73]:

```
ax = df.plot.scatter(x='SrcToObject', y='SrcToDetector', color=(.0,.25,1,0.3))
xlabel=ax.set_xlabel("source to object distance (" + descsc['SrcToObject'].unit + ")")
```

```
ylabel=ax.set_ylabel("source to imaging distance (" + descs['SrcToDetector'].unit + ")")
```


Plotting that ratio gives the geometric magnification

In [62]:

```
if descs['SrcToObject'].unit == descs['SrcToDetector'].unit:  
    ax = (df.SrcToDetector / df.SrcToObject).plot.hist(logy=True, edgecolor='black', color=(0,1,.5))  
    label = ax.set_xlabel("geometric magnification")
```

